

not seen being far down field. The ν C=O of carboxylic group, as expected, was at 1690 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectrum, whereas it was at 1730 cm^{-1} in the case of the methyl ester.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Kofler hot stage m.p. apparatus and are uncorrected. Chlorine analysis was done by oxygen flask method. I.R. spectrum was taken on Unicam SP 1000 infra red spectrophotometer. NMR was recorded on Varian A-60 NMR-spectrophotometer (TMS as internal reference). Mass spectrum was taken on A.E.I. mass spectrometer, model MS9.

Methyl-(α -Chloro- β -3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate (II)

A solution of 54.0 g. (1.8 mols) of piperonal and 47.4 ml. (2.7 mols) of methyl chloroacetate were slowly added under stirring to 12.42 g. (2.7 g atoms) sodium in 180 ml. dry methanol chilled to -10° in an ice salt bath. The addition of the mixture was complete in 3 hr. The stirring was continued for another 2 hr at -5° and then left overnight at room temperature. The mixture was poured into ice water (700 ml) containing acetic acid (4 ml). The white crystalline solid separated was collected, washed with cold water and dried in vacuum dessicator, yield nearly 90%. The crude dry powder was dissolved by boiling in a large volume of petroleum ether (b.p. 60° - 80°). The clear solution was decanted and allowed to cool overnight inside a refrigerator. Out of the two types of crystals formed, only the bunches of flaky needles adhering to the sides were collected and the lumpy crystalline solids of the epoxy ester at the bottom of the flask were not taken out. The flaky needles were recrystallised to give the colourless needles of methyl-(α -chloro- β -3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate (II), m.p. 136° (lit.³ 136°); yield 50%; Found: C, 54.91; H, 3.86; Cl, 14.65%; Calc. for $C_{11}H_9O_4Cl$: C, 54.88; H, 3.74; Cl, 14.76%.

α -Chloro- β -(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid (I)

The above methyl ester (II) (5 g.), sodium hydroxide (25 ml., 2N) was boiled till the compound completely dissolved. On cooling the solution, the sodium salt (III) separated out and collected, yield nearly 85%. The sodium salt was then suspended in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid to afford a solid product which was collected, washed with water and dried. On recrystallising from aqueous alcohol afforded the stout prismatic crystals of α -chloro- β -(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid (I), m.p. 220° , yield about 65%. The compound responded to Beilstein test for chlorine. Found: C, 53.50; H, 3.24; Cl, 15.37%. $C_{10}H_7O_4Cl$ requires: C, 52.98; H, 3.09; Cl, 15.48%. I.R. $\nu_{\text{Max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1690 cm^{-1} (S) (Carboxylic C=O); 1610 cm^{-1} (M) (Ar C=C). NMR (DMSO) 6.15δ (S, 2H, -O-CH₂-O-); 7.05δ (d, 1H, Ar C-5 proton, $J_{\text{Ortho}} = 7.50$ Cps); 7.50δ (poorly resolved, appearing as d, 1H, Ar C-6 proton, $J_{\text{Ortho}} = 7.50$ Cps; $J_{\text{Meta}} = 0.8$ Cps); 7.60δ (S with slight bifurcation and

overlapped with C-6 proton signal, 1H, Ar C-2 proton, $J_{\text{Meta}} = 0.8$ Cps); 7.90δ (S, 1H, vinylic proton). Mass spectrum: The mass spectrum of the compound revealed the characteristic abundance ratio of M and M+2 peaks in 3 : 1, corresponding to Cl^{35} and Cl^{37} . Significant fragments occurred at m/e 228 (M+2, 30%), 226 (M+, base peak), 190 (M-HCl, 80%), 121 (M-HCl, -C₂-COOH, 80%).

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Synthesis of 1, 2-disubstituted-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-4-quinazoline thiones

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HUNIG and Hubner¹ have reported that reaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate with 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexane gives benzoxazine-4-thione derivatives. Carney *et al.*² reported that 1,3-benzoxazine-4-thiones undergo reaction with aromatic amines giving quinazoline-thiones. However, in a three component system—1-morpholinocyclohexane, benzoyl isothiocyanate and arylamine—direct formation of the same quinazoline thione has limitations—thiourea being the major product. Solvent used in these condensations is of vital importance. Benzene or ethanol gives mainly thiourea. If tetrahydrofuran is used as a solvent the major product is quinazoline thione. This suggests that the intermediate formed must be an adduct which then cyclises to quinazoline derivative or first intermediate is 1,2-cyclo addition product—oxazine thione—which further undergoes reaction with arylamine to quinazoline thiones. Both these possibilities are confirmed by the fact that benzoxazines can be converted to quinazoline thiones. Benzoyl isothiocyanate was condensed with anilino cyclohexene in ether and the adduct obtained when refluxed in tetrahydrofuran afforded

* Work done at B.C.J. College, Cambay.

NOTES

TABLE—1,2-DISUBSTITUTED ARYL-5,6,7,8-TETRAHYDRO-4-QUINAZOLINETHIONES

No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% Sulphur	
						Theoretical	Found
1.	H	H	127-28	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S	10.1	9.4
*2.	H	OCH ₃	154-55	49	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	9.2	8.8
3.	H	NO ₂	104	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.8	8.6
*4.	H	CH ₃	156-58	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	9.6	9.5
**5.	H	Br	115	51	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SBr	8.1	7.6
6.	Br	H	97	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SBr	8.1	7.7
7.	Br	NO ₂	90	48	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ SBr	7.3	6.9
8.	Br	CH ₃	103	48	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ SBr	7.8	7.4
9.	Br	Br	94	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBr ₂	6.7	6.5
10.	Br	Cl	75	48	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBrCl	7.4	7.0
**11.	Cl	H	87	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SCl	9.1	8.7
**12.	Cl	OCH ₃	67	46	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OSCl	8.4	8.4
13.	Cl	CH ₃	138	49	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ SCl	8.7	8.6
14.	Cl	Br	74	46	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBrCl	7.4	7.0
**15.	Cl	Cl	130-31	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SCl ₂	8.3	8.0

* These compounds show mild antihistaminic activity compared to Mepyramine maleate.

** These compounds show weak antifungal activity compared to Grisofulvin.

the quinazolino thione, also available directly by three component systems discussed above.

In the present study, 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexene was condensed with benzoyl isothiocyanates and aryl amines in tetrahydrofuran. The products obtained were 1,2-disubstituted aryl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-quinazoline thiones, some of these were confirmed via the oxazine thione route. Some of these compounds showed very mild antifungal activities and antihistamine activity. Table describes the compounds prepared.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

Typical procedure for the synthesis is described below :

Benzoyl isothiocyanates were prepared by known methods. 1-Morpholino-1-cyclohexene was prepared according to Hunig *et al.*³

1-o-Methoxyphenyl-2-phenyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-quinazolinethione :

A mixture of 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexene (1.024 g; 0.006 mole), benzoyl isothiocyanate (1 g; 0.006 mole) and *c*-anisidine (1.511 g; 0.0123 mole) in tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) was refluxed on a boiling water bath for 4 hr. On cooling, the product obtained was filtered (crude melts at 148°-50°). It was recrystallized from tetrahydrofuran and melted at 154°-55°.

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Cyanoethylation of Sulphonamides

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MISRA *et al.*¹⁻³ and Shukla *et al.*⁴ in their earlier communications have reported the cyanoethylation of benzylphenyl sulphones, benzyl sulphonamides, benzene sulphonamides and *N*-substituted sulphonamides. Among them *p*-chlorobenzylphenyl sulphone was found to be very effective followed by the *o*-chlorobenzyl phenyl sulphone. All the compounds showed considerable toxicity to housefly (*Musca nebulosa*). These workers found that the introduction of cyanoethyl group increases the effectiveness of the drug.

Sulpha drugs have strong bacteriostatic properties. It was therefore, considered worthwhile to modify the structure of these compounds by superimposing the toxophoric group -CH₂CH₂CN on them and test for their insecticidal activity, in view of the excellent results achieved earlier.

Cyanoethylation of sulphanilamide and sulphapyridine was reported⁵ with acrylonitrile in dioxane solvent using sodium hydroxide as catalyst.

In the present communication, we have synthesized the cyanoethylated products of some more sulphonamides with acrylonitrile in dioxane solvent using benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (Triton B) as catalyst with a view to finding out some more potential insecticides.

It is noticed that sulphanilamide when cyanoethylated in acetic acid medium, the active hydrogen atoms of the amido and *p*-amino groups were cyanoethylated.